

Participatory tools

ACTOR ID

SETTING UP THE PROJECT: BUILDING THE CO-INNOVATION PROJECT TOGETHER

How to engage all project partners in the design of the project?

This part concerns the period where it is necessary to detail the actions, the tasks and who does what. The aims are already clarified, and the partnership is as stable as possible.

Probably the fastest way to construct a project is for the person who has the idea to build it, but this approach will lose all the richness of a group, and the rest of the project will probably be even more complicated. A preferred option is to involve all the project's actors in defining the project's limits, the problems to be solved, the different contexts, the actors who will be concerned (closely or by far), and the beneficiaries.

Not only will each bring their ideas, networks, and contexts, but they will also appropriate the subject more easily. They will get to know each other, work together, and be more efficient during the project. All the actors will feel more involved and engaged with the project.

How to solve it

You can bring together all the actors you have already identified who could be part of the project. Each time new stakeholders are identified; they need to be involved in the process.

Reflection tools allow everyone to express themselves. It is the beginning of the project; it is the moment to give all the ideas and not restrict yourself.

Word of advice

Be careful! Preparing the project with several people can take a long time. Therefore, plan even more time than seems necessary so that the project has time to mature.

You can involve the actors in the writing of the project by sharing the parts to be written.

Take your time. So that each actor finds their place before the project begins. The time you take is an investment for the future.

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One example of a tool to facilitate this stage

Actor ID – The right skill for the right task

Description of the tool

- **What:** Engage people to participate, which is crucial at the team-building stage and often at the pre-project phase. The Actor ID tool can then be used iteratively throughout the project to identify a collection of tasks for completion, and the competencies required to undertake them.
- **How long:** 30 mins-2 hrs
- **How many:** Used in small, nascent groups, particularly in the pre-funding stage
- **What you'll need:** flip chart paper, sticky notes, markers

Steps:

- Brainstorming tasks: Ask participants to brainstorm tasks for project/initiative development, summarizing the task on a sticky-note
- Clustering tasks into roles: Ask participants to cluster similar tasks together/tasks that need a particular skill set.
- Ask participants to choose a cluster of tasks and present it to the group. Verify if it is comprehensive, complete, and in the right cluster. Identify with the participants the skill sets required, the resources needed, and who will take responsibility for each task.
- Allocation/adoption of roles with matchsticks

- Creating plans for roles and how and when tasks will be undertaken: Participants have agreed to take a role and can be invited to work alone or as a team (where two or more participants are working on a task).
- Plan a follow-up meeting to assess progress

Testimony of the use

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The H2020 Skin project is a project on developing short food chains. The project brought together different communities of actors within each country, composed of diverse actors (with different backgrounds, types of knowledge etc.).

In Ireland, they used the "Actor ID" tool. The tool aims to assign tasks to actors based on their competencies, skills, forms of experience, and, perhaps most importantly, interests. Taking a role that they're interested in can energize participation and engagement. If the person doesn't have the required experience or background in the area, they can be paired with someone more experienced in a kind of a buddy system, or the task can be undertaken as a group.

Actor ID was a way of identifying ways for people to diversify their skillset and learn things that they found energizing. Furthermore, there's the practical aspect to ensuring that particular types of expertise, knowledge and experience held by different actors are fully leveraged. The project benefits from the complementarity of the kinds of experience and expertise in the multi-actor group, which is maximised by

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strategically pairing people to the right tasks.

Tips:

- This tool can be used at different project stages whenever there is a need to assign tasks to several people.
- It is easy to understand and use by novice facilitators.
- Another tool that can be used in similar circumstances is “brainstorm”

